

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**A NOVEL ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND
VALIDATION OF REVERSE PHASE-HPLC FOR THE
ESTIMATION OF DACOMITINIB IN BULK AND MARKETED
PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORMS****Dr. Madireddy Mamata**

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Abstract:

A rapid and precise reverse phase high performance liquid chromatographic method has been developed for the validated of Dacomitinib, in its pure form as well as in tablet dosage form. Chromatography was carried out on a Xterra C18 (4.6 x 150mm, 5µm) column using a mixture of Methanol and DMF (45:55% v/v) as the mobile phase at a flow rate of 0.8ml/min, the detection was carried out at 260nm. The retention time of the Dacomitinib was 2.379 ±0.02min respectively. The method produce linear responses in the concentration range of 24-120mg/ml of Dacomitinib. The method precision for the determination of assay was below 2.0%RSD. The method is useful in the quality control of bulk and pharmaceutical formulations. The method was validated for accuracy, precision, linearity, robustness, ruggedness and LOD & LOQ of standard solution. The developed RP-HPLC method was found to be accurate, precise, linear, and robust and was successful applied to a pharmaceutical tablet formulation for qualitative estimation of Dacomitinib in Bulk form and Marketed Pharmaceutical Dosage forms.

Key Words: Dacomitinib, RP-HPLC, Method Development, Validation, Accuracy.

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Please cite this article in press Madireddy Mamata et al., A Novel Analytical Method Development And Validation Of Reverse Phase-HPLC For The Estimation Of Dacomitinib In Bulk And Marketed Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (04).

INTRODUCTION:

Dacomitinib is a member of the class of quinazolines that is 7-methoxyquinazoline-4,6-diamine in which the amino group at position 4 is substituted by a 3-chloro-4-fluorophenyl group and the amino group at position 6 is substituted by an (E)-4-(piperidin-1-yl) but-2-enoyl group¹. It has a role as an epidermal growth factor receptor antagonist and an antineoplastic agent. It is a member of quinazolines, a member of piperidines, an enamide, and a member of mono chlorobenzenes, a member of mono fluoro benzenes, a tertiary amino compound, a secondary amino compound and a secondary carboxamide. Dacomitinib, designed as (2E)-N-16-4-(piperidin-1-yl) but-2-enamide, is an oral highly selective

Quinazalone part of the second-generation tyrosine kinase inhibitors which are characterized by the irreversible binding at the ATP domain of the epidermal growth factor receptor family kinase domains. Some evidence in the literature suggests the therapeutic potential of Dacomitinib in the epithelial ovarian cancer model, although further investigations are needed. Dacomitinib is a multi-kinase receptor inhibitor used in the therapy of cases of non-small cell lung cancer that harbor activating mutations in the epidermal growth factor receptor gene (EGFR). Dacomitinib is associated with high rate of transient serum aminotransferase elevations during therapy but has not been linked to instances of clinically apparent acute liver injury.

Fig-1: Chemical Structure of Dacomitinib

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Table-1: Instruments used

S.No.	Instruments and Glasswares	Model
1	HPLC	WATERS Alliance 2695 separation module, Software: Empower 2, PDA 996 Detector.
2	pH meter	Lab India
3	Weighing machine	Sartorius
4	Volumetric flasks	Borosil
5	Pipettes and Burettes	Borosil
6	Beakers	Borosil
7	Digital ultra sonicator	Labman

Table-2: Chemicals Used

S.No.	Chemical	Brand Names
1	Dacomitinib (Pure)	Syncorp laboratories
2	DMF and Methanol for HPLC	LICHROSOLV (MERCK)
3	Acetonitrile for HPLC	Merck

HPLC Method Development:**Preparation of Standard Solution:**

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Dacomitinib working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Methanol and sonicate to dissolve and removal of air completely and make volume up to the mark with the same Methanol.

Further pipette 0.72ml of the above Dacomitinib stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Methanol.

Procedure:

Inject the samples by changing the chromatographic conditions and record the chromatograms, note the conditions of proper peak elution for performing validation parameters as per ICH guidelines.

Mobile Phase Optimization:

Initially the mobile phase tried was methanol: DMF and Acetonitrile: Water with varying proportions. Finally, the mobile phase⁴ was optimized to Methanol and DMF in proportion 45:55 v/v respectively.

Optimization of Column:

The method was performed with various C18 columns like ODS column, symmetry and X Bridge C18 column. Xterra C18 (4.6 x 150mm, 5µm) was found to be ideal as it gave good peak shape and resolution at 1ml/min flow.

Preparation of Mobile Phase:

Accurately measured 450 ml (45%) of HPLC Methanol and 550 ml of HPLC DMF (55%) were mixed and degassed in a digital ultrasonicator for 10 minutes and then filtered through 0.45 µ filter under vacuum filtration.

Diluent Preparation:

The Mobile phase was used as the diluent.

Procedure:

Inject the three replicate injections of standard and sample solutions and calculate the assay⁷ by using formula:

% ASSAY =

$$\frac{\text{Sample area}}{\text{Standard area}} \times \frac{\text{Weight of standard}}{\text{Dilution of standard}} \times \frac{\text{Dilution of sample}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times \frac{\text{Purity}}{100} \times \frac{\text{Weight of tablet}}{\text{Label claim}} \times 100$$

Validation Parameters**System Suitability**

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Dacomitinib working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.72ml of the above Dacomitinib stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

Procedure:

The standard solution was injected for five times and measured the area for all five injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of five replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits.

Specificity:**Preparation of Standard Solution:**

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Dacomitinib working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.72ml of the above Dacomitinib stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

Preparation of Sample Solution:

Take average weight of the Tablet and crush in a mortar by using pestle and weight 10 mg equivalent weight of Dacomitinib sample into a 10mL clean dry volumetric flask and add about 7mL of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent⁶.

Further pipette 0.72ml of Dacomitinib above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent.

Linearity:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Dacomitinib working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Preparation of Level – I (24ppm of Dacomitinib):

Pipette out 0.24ml of stock solution in to a 10ml volumetric flask and make up the volume up to mark by using diluent.

Preparation of Level – II (48ppm of Dacomitinib):

Pipette out 0.48ml of stock solution in to a 10ml volumetric flask and make up the volume up to mark by using diluent.

Preparation of Level – III (72ppm of Dacomitinib):

Pipette out 0.72ml of stock solution in to a 10ml volumetric flask and make up the volume up to mark by using diluent.

Preparation of Level – IV (96ppm of Dacomitinib):

Pipette out 0.96ml of stock solution⁸ in to a 10ml volumetric flask and make up the volume up to mark by using diluent.

Preparation of Level – V (120ppm of Dacomitinib):

Pipette out 1.2ml of stock solution in to a 10ml volumetric flask and make up the volume up to mark by using diluent.

Procedure:

Inject each level into the chromatographic system⁹ and measure the peak area.

Plot a graph of peak area versus concentration (on X-axis concentration and on Y-axis Peak area) and calculate the correlation coefficient.

Precision**Repeatability****Preparation of Dacomitinib Product Solution for Precision:**

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Dacomitinib working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.72 ml of the above Dacomitinib stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

The standard solution was injected for five times and measured the area for all five injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of five replicate injections¹⁰ was found to be within the specified limits.

Intermediate Precision:

To evaluate the intermediate precision (also known as Ruggedness) of the method, Precision was performed on different days by maintaining same conditions.

Procedure:**Day 1:**

The standard solution was injected for six times and measured the area for all six injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of six replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits.

Day 2:

The standard solution was injected for six times and measured the area for all six injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of six replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits.

Accuracy:**For preparation of 50% Standard stock solution:**

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Dacomitinib working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.36ml of the above Dacomitinib stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

For preparation of 100% Standard stock solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Dacomitinib working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.72ml of the above Dacomitinib stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

For preparation of 150% Standard stock solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Dacomitinib working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 1.08ml of the above Dacomitinib stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents¹².

Procedure:

Inject the Three replicate injections of individual concentrations (50%, 100%, 150%) were made under the optimized conditions. Recorded the chromatograms and measured the peak responses. Calculate the Amount found and Amount added for Dacomitinib and calculate the individual recovery and mean recovery values.

Robustness:

The analysis was performed in different conditions to find the variability of test results¹⁵. The following conditions are checked for variation of results. .

For preparation of Standard solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Dacomitinib working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.72ml of the above Dacomitinib stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

Effect of Variation of flow conditions:

The sample was analyzed at 0.7 ml/min and 0.9 ml/min instead of 0.8ml/min, remaining conditions are same. 10 μ l of the above sample was injected and chromatograms were recorded

Effect of Variation of Mobile Phase Organic Composition:

The sample was analyzed by variation of mobile phase i.e. Methanol: Water was taken in the ratio and 40:60, 50:50 instead of 45:55, remaining conditions are same. 10 μ l of the above sample was injected and chromatograms were recorded.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**Optimization of Method:****Optimized Chromatogram Conditions:**

Mobile phase ratio : Methanol: DMF (45:55% v/v)
Column : Xterra C18 (4.6 \times 150mm) 5 μ m
Column temperature : 40 $^{\circ}$ C
Wavelength : 260nm
Flow rate : 0.8ml/min
Injection volume : 10 μ l
Run time : 6minutes

Fig-2: Optimized Chromatogram

Validation of the Developed Method

The developed method was validated for linearity, system suitability, precision, accuracy, robustness, specificity, LOD and LOQ according to ICH guide lines.

System Suitability Test

System suitability test was carried out initially with mobile phase followed by injecting 5 injections of the same concentration. Continual injections were injected to assess the suitability of system for developed method on each day of method validation. Features including % RSD, tailing factor, and theoretical plate were calculated.

Table-3: Results of System Suitability for Dacomitinib

S.No.	Peak Name	RT	Area (μV*sec)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Dacomitinib	2.317	2274631	239458	5728	1.2
2	Dacomitinib	2.302	2284721	239582	5093	1.2
3	Dacomitinib	2.323	2238127	236493	5391	1.2
4	Dacomitinib	2.343	2259349	249482	6139	1.2
5	Dacomitinib	2.321	2204850	239452	5281	1.2
Mean			2252336			
Std. Dev.			31827.08			
% RSD			1.41307			

Specificity

The ICH documents define specificity as the ability to assess unequivocally the analyte in the presence of components that may be expected to be present, such as impurities, degradation products, and matrix components. Analytical method was tested for specificity to measure accurately quantities Dacomitinib in drug product.

%ASSAY =

$$\frac{\text{Sample area}}{\text{Standard area}} \times \frac{\text{Weight of standard}}{\text{Dilution of standard}} \times \frac{\text{Dilution of sample}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times \frac{\text{Purity}}{100} \times \frac{\text{Weight of tablet}}{\text{Label claim}} \times 100$$

The % purity of Dacomitinib in pharmaceutical dosage form was found to be 99.7%.

Linearity (Calibration Curve)

The linearity of drug was determined by preparing different dilutions of drug in the concentration range of 24 to 120ng/mL. A calibration curve was constructed by taking concentrations at x-axis and peaks areas on the y-axis and coefficient of correlation¹⁸ (R²) was determined.

Chromatographic Data for Linearity Study:**Table-4: Linearity Data of Dacomitinib**

Concentration Level (%)	Concentration μg/ml	Average Peak Area
33	24	791554
66	48	1647073
100	72	2283804
133	96	3058339
166	120	3839630

Linearity Plot:

The plot of Concentration (x) versus the Average Peak Area (y) data of Dacomitinib is a straight line.

$$Y = mx + c$$

$$\text{Slope (m)} = 31709$$

$$\text{Intercept (c)} = 34216$$

$$\text{Correlation Coefficient (r)} = 0.998$$

Validation Criteria: The response linearity is verified if the Correlation Coefficient is 0.99 or greater.

Conclusion: Correlation Coefficient (r) is 0.99, and the intercept is 34216. These values meet the validation criteria.

Precision:

The precision¹⁹ of an analytical procedure expresses the closeness of agreement (degree of scatter) between a series of measurements obtained from multiple sampling of the same homogeneous sample under the prescribed conditions.

Repeatability

Obtained Five (5) replicates of 100% accuracy solution as per experimental conditions. Recorded the peak areas and calculated % RSD.

Table-5: Results of Repeatability for Dacomitinib:

S. No.	Peak Name	Retention time	Area ($\mu\text{V} \cdot \text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Dacomitinib	2.356	2259464	245362	5938	1.2
2	Dacomitinib	2.356	2275915	248293	5827	1.2
3	Dacomitinib	2.357	2282117	240795	5032	1.2
4	Dacomitinib	2.358	2278675	230139	5978	1.2
5	Dacomitinib	2.359	2282448	249605	6183	1.2
Mean			2275724			
Std. Dev			9476.485			
%RSD			0.416416			

Intermediate Precision:

Analyst1:

Table-6: Results of Intermediate precision for Dacomitinib

S.No.	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V} \cdot \text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate count	USP Tailing
1	Dacomitinib	2.380	2236184	202188	5472	1.2
2	Dacomitinib	2.383	2238020	201837	6193	1.2
3	Dacomitinib	2.385	2239352	201273	5980	1.2
4	Dacomitinib	2.385	2242466	203923	7163	1.2
5	Dacomitinib	2.389	2244692	202938	6182	1.2
6	Dacomitinib	2.389	2247654	201982	7684	1.2
Mean			2241395			
Std. Dev.			4333.851			
% RSD			0.193355			

Analyst 2:

Table-7: Results of Intermediate Precision Analyst 2 for Dacomitinib

S.No.	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate count	USP Tailing
1	Dacomitinib	2.380	2236184	217363	5928	1.2
2	Dacomitinib	2.383	2238020	218467	6183	1.2
3	Dacomitinib	2.385	2239352	218346	5927	1.2
4	Dacomitinib	2.385	2242466	221736	5163	1.2
5	Dacomitinib	2.389	2244692	228361	4827	1.2
6	Dacomitinib	2.346	2263431	217553	5019	1.2
Mean			2244024			
Std. Dev.			9988.458			
% RSD			0.445114			

Accuracy:

Accuracy at different concentrations (50%, 100%, and 150%) was prepared and the % recovery was calculated.

Table-8: The Accuracy Results for Dacomitinib

% Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (ppm)	Amount Found (ppm)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	1172485	36	35.8	99.4	99.5%
100%	2314753	72	71.6	99.4	
150%	3480210	108	107.9	99.9	

Limit of Detection

The detection limit²⁰ of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample which can be detected but not necessarily quantitated as an exact value.

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times \sigma / s$$

Where

 σ = Standard deviation of the response

S = Slope of the calibration curve

Result:=5.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ **Quantitation Limit**

The quantitation limit²¹ of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample which can be quantitatively determined.

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times \sigma / S$$

Where

 σ = Standard deviation of the response

S = Slope of the calibration curve

Result:

=16.7 μ g/ml

Robustness

The robustness was performed for the flow rate variations from 0.7 ml/min to 0.9ml/min and mobile

phase ratio variation from more organic phase to less organic phase ratio for Dacomitinib. The method is robust only in less flow condition and the method is robust even by change in the Mobile phase \pm 5%. The standard and samples of Dacomitinib were injected by changing the conditions of chromatography. There was no significant change in the parameters like resolution, tailing factor, asymmetric factor, and plate count.

Table-9: Results for Robustness

Parameter used for Sample Analysis	Peak Area	Retention Time	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor
Actual Flow rate of 0.8mL/min	3119086	2.379	5837	1.2
Less Flow rate of 0.7mL/min	2640811	2.763	5361	1.2
More Flow rate of 0.9mL/min	2640354	2.234	5231	1.2
Less organic phase	2640758	2.765	4503	1.5
More organic phase	2640125	2.236	4491	1.5

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

The analytical method was developed by studying different parameters. First of all, maximum absorbance was found to be at 260nm and the peak purity was excellent. Injection volume was selected to be 10 μ l which gave a good peak area. The column used for study was Xterra C₁₈ because it was giving good peak. 40 ° C temperatures was found to be suitable for the nature of drug solution. The flow rate was fixed at 0.8ml/min because of good peak area and satisfactory retention time. Mobile phase is Methanol: DMF was fixed due to good symmetrical peak. So this mobile phase was used for the proposed study. Methanol: DMF was selected because of maximum extraction sonication time was fixed to be 10min at which all the drug particles were completely soluble and showed good recovery. Run time was selected to be 6min because analyze gave peak around 2.3 and also to reduce the total run time. The percent recovery was found to be 98.0-102 was linear and precise over the same range. Both system and method precision was found to be accurate and well within range. The analytical method was found linearity over the range of 24-120ppm of the Dacomitinib target concentration. The analytical passed both robustness and ruggedness tests. On both cases, relative standard deviation was well satisfactory.

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